

ChatGPT's Understanding of History: A Comparison to Vietnamese Students and its Potential in History Education

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Abstract: *As technology continues to advance, the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has become increasingly prominent. ChatGPT, a language model developed by OpenAI, has demonstrated remarkable abilities in understanding history similar to Vietnamese students. This paper examines the role of ChatGPT in history teaching and learning in Vietnam. Through an analysis of ChatGPT's performance in history exams and a comparison with Vietnamese students' scores, it is evident that ChatGPT has achieved a commendable level of proficiency in the subject. The potential of ChatGPT in history learning and teaching is explored, highlighting its ability to provide personalized assistance, enhance critical thinking skills, and supplement traditional instructional methods. While ChatGPT shows promise, further research is needed to ensure its alignment with the educational standards and requirements of the Vietnamese curriculum. This paper concludes by emphasizing the need for a balanced approach that combines the strengths of AI technology with the guidance of experienced educators to create a comprehensive and effective history learning environment.*

Keywords: ChatGPT, history teaching, history learning, artificial intelligence, Vietnamese curriculum.

I. Introduction

ChatGPT² is an advanced natural language processing (NLP) model developed by OpenAI, utilizing AI and deep learning techniques. It employs a transformer architecture to analyze input data and produce appropriate outputs. Built upon the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) network architecture, ChatGPT leverages vast internet data to grasp language syntax, semantics, and structure. Notably, ChatGPT's distinguishing feature is its ability to continuously learn and improve by training on new data, leading to

increased accuracy and informativeness over time based on user feedback.

The GPT-4 version of ChatGPT has showcased human-like performance on specific tasks, particularly those at the high school level. This indicates that ChatGPT can generate text that is virtually indistinguishable from human-written content. Its remarkable capabilities offer exciting prospects for its application in various educational contexts, empowering students and educators alike with an advanced language model that adapts and enhances its proficiency with continuous learning [1].

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² <https://chat.openai.com/>

Hana et al. [2], [3], [4] conducted various research on the use of ChatGPT in Vietnamese education and indicated its potential contributions to administrators, instructors, and students.

Quy et al. examined the performance of ChatGPT on the Vietnamese National High School Graduation Examination in a series of studies [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], which covers disciplines such as mathematics, literature, English, physics, chemistry, biology, history, geography, and civic education. According to the conclusions of these research, ChatGPT exhibits broad competency in the test, with an average score of 6-7 for both natural and social science combinations. ChatGPT demonstrated average performance in the subjects of mathematics, physics, chemistry, and biology, while exhibiting superior performance in English, literature, history, geography, and civic education.

The field of education holds paramount importance in shaping individuals and societies, and history, as a discipline, plays a particularly significant role in imparting a comprehensive understanding of the past. In recent times, the emergence of AI and natural language processing has introduced language models like ChatGPT, which possess substantial potential to transform the methods of history teaching and learning. This paper explores the abilities of ChatGPT in understanding history, analyzes its performance in history exams, and investigates its potential role in history teaching and learning in Vietnam.

II. ChatGPT's abilities in history

To assess ChatGPT's proficiency in history, its performance in answering history test questions was evaluated over a five-year period (2019-2023). Table 1 presents the accuracy of ChatGPT's answers, which steadily improved from 42.5% in 2019 to 77.5% in 2023, with an average performance of 56.5%. These

results indicate that ChatGPT has shown remarkable progress in comprehending historical concepts and facts.

Figure 1 compares the history subject scores of Vietnamese students with ChatGPT's scores from 2019 to 2022. Notably, ChatGPT achieved scores ranging from 4.25 to 7.75, which closely align with the scores of Vietnamese students in most cases. This suggests that ChatGPT's proficiency in history is comparable to that of the majority of Vietnamese students, indicating its potential as a valuable tool in history education.

Table 1: Performance of ChatGPT (%) [10]

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	AVG
ChatGPT	42.5	47.5	55	60	77.5	56.5

Figure 1. Comparison in history [10].

III. Potential of ChatGPT in history education

In this section, we pose three questions to ChatGPT, exploring the potential of ChatGPT in the context of teaching and learning history in Vietnam.

Prompt: *How is ChatGPT's Vietnamese history ability?*

ChatGPT: *As an AI language model, ChatGPT's understanding of Vietnamese history is dependent on the data it has been trained on, which includes a wide range of texts in multiple languages. While ChatGPT has the potential to provide information and insights on various historical topics, including Vietnamese history, it is important to note that its knowledge is*

derived from patterns learned from the training data and may not capture all specific details or nuances related to Vietnamese history.

ChatGPT's ability to respond to questions and provide information about Vietnamese history can vary. It may offer general knowledge, historical events, key figures, or broad perspectives on certain topics. However, it is crucial to approach ChatGPT's responses with a critical mindset and corroborate the information provided with reliable sources specific to Vietnamese history.

To enhance ChatGPT's understanding of Vietnamese history, ongoing research and development efforts are necessary. These efforts may involve fine-tuning the model with more specific and relevant training data focused on Vietnamese history, incorporating feedback from historians and subject matter experts, and continuously refining the model to improve its accuracy and contextual understanding of Vietnamese historical events and contexts.

While ChatGPT can provide a starting point for exploring Vietnamese history, it should not replace the expertise of historians, educators, and reliable historical sources. Human guidance and interpretation are essential for providing deeper insights, critical analysis, and a comprehensive understanding of Vietnamese history. Therefore, it is important to utilize ChatGPT as a tool alongside human expertise to enhance the teaching and learning of Vietnamese history.

Prompt: How can ChatGPT help Vietnamese high school teachers teach History?

ChatGPT: *ChatGPT can be a valuable tool for Vietnamese high school teachers in teaching history by providing various forms of support and resources. Here are some ways ChatGPT can help Vietnamese high school teachers in history education:*

- *Access to Information: ChatGPT can provide teachers with access to a vast amount of historical information and resources. Teachers can use ChatGPT to quickly retrieve specific facts, dates, or details about historical events, figures, or concepts. This access to a wide range of information can enhance teachers' preparation for lessons and enable them to provide accurate and up-to-date content to their students.*
- *Lesson Planning and Resource Creation: ChatGPT can assist teachers in developing lesson plans and creating teaching resources. Teachers can interact with ChatGPT to gather ideas, brainstorm activities, and generate engaging discussion questions. Additionally, ChatGPT can recommend supplementary materials such as articles, primary sources, or multimedia content, which teachers can incorporate into their lessons to provide additional perspectives and resources for students.*
- *Personalized Assistance: ChatGPT can provide personalized assistance to both teachers and students. Teachers can seek clarification or explanations on historical topics, enabling them to better understand complex concepts and ensure accurate content delivery. This personalized assistance can help teachers address their own knowledge gaps and enhance their confidence in teaching history effectively.*
- *Student Support: ChatGPT can be utilized as a resource for students in and outside of the classroom. Teachers can guide students in interacting with ChatGPT to seek answers to specific historical questions or engage in*

discussions on historical topics. This fosters independent learning, encourages students to explore historical content further, and provides additional support to students who may require extra assistance.

- *Promoting Critical Thinking:* ChatGPT can be used as a tool to prompt critical thinking and analysis. Teachers can encourage students to evaluate ChatGPT's responses, compare them with other sources, and engage in discussions about the reliability, biases, and interpretations of the information provided. This helps students develop critical thinking skills and a deeper understanding of historical events.
- *Language Support:* ChatGPT can assist teachers in providing language support for students. Teachers can use ChatGPT to assist with translations, explanations of complex historical terminology, or clarification of historical concepts in both Vietnamese and English. This support can be particularly beneficial for students who may struggle with language barriers when learning history.
- *Continuous Professional Development:* ChatGPT can serve as a resource for teachers' continuous professional development. Teachers can interact with ChatGPT to explore new historical perspectives, stay updated with research findings, and seek recommendations for further reading or professional development opportunities in the field of history education.

It is important to note that while ChatGPT can provide valuable support, it should not replace the expertise and guidance of teachers. Human interaction, interpretation, and contextualization are

vital in facilitating meaningful historical discussions, fostering critical thinking, and providing a comprehensive understanding of history. Therefore, ChatGPT should be seen as a supplementary tool that complements the expertise and pedagogical skills of high school teachers in Vietnam.

Prompt: How can ChatGPT help Vietnamese high school students learning History?

ChatGPT: ChatGPT can be a beneficial tool for Vietnamese high school students in learning history by providing support, resources, and opportunities for engagement. Here are some ways ChatGPT can assist Vietnamese high school students in history education:

- *Personalized Assistance:* ChatGPT can provide personalized assistance to students, addressing their specific questions and clarifying historical concepts. Students can interact with ChatGPT to seek explanations, definitions, or additional information related to historical events, figures, or themes. This personalized support can help students grasp difficult concepts and enhance their understanding of history.
- *Access to Information:* ChatGPT can offer a vast repository of historical knowledge and resources. Students can use ChatGPT to quickly access factual information, dates, or details about historical events, helping them in their research or preparation for exams and assignments. This access to information promotes independent learning and empowers students to explore historical topics further.
- *Supplementary Resources:* ChatGPT can recommend supplementary materials such as articles, books, primary sources, or multimedia content to supplement students'

understanding of historical topics. These resources can provide additional perspectives, diverse viewpoints, and in-depth analysis, enriching students' exploration and critical engagement with historical content.

- *Promoting Critical Thinking: ChatGPT can encourage critical thinking skills by presenting alternative perspectives and challenging students to evaluate historical evidence. Students can engage in discussions with ChatGPT, compare its responses with other sources, and analyze the reliability, biases, and interpretations of the information provided. This fosters critical thinking, analytical skills, and a deeper understanding of historical events.*
- *Guided Inquiry: Students can utilize ChatGPT for guided inquiry activities, where they can formulate historical questions and seek answers. ChatGPT can assist students in exploring different aspects of historical topics, suggesting avenues for further research, and guiding them in evaluating the credibility and relevance of sources. This promotes independent inquiry and enhances students' research skills.*
- *Language Support: ChatGPT can aid students in understanding historical terminology, translating texts, or clarifying complex concepts in both Vietnamese and English. This language support can assist students in overcoming language barriers and accessing historical information in a more comprehensible manner.*
- *24/7 Availability: ChatGPT's accessibility at any time allows students to seek historical*

assistance beyond classroom hours. Students can access ChatGPT for quick queries, to review historical facts, or to gain insights even when direct teacher guidance is not available. This promotes independent learning and flexibility in engaging with historical content.

While ChatGPT can be a valuable resource, it is important for students to approach its responses critically and cross-reference information with reliable historical sources. It should be seen as a tool to supplement students' learning experiences, complementing the guidance and expertise of their history teachers. By utilizing ChatGPT in these ways, Vietnamese high school students can enhance their understanding of history, develop critical thinking skills, access additional resources, and engage in independent exploration of historical topics.

ChatGPT holds significant potential in enhancing history teaching and learning in Vietnam. Its capabilities include personalized assistance, provision of additional resources, and fostering critical thinking skills. By interacting with ChatGPT, students can receive tailored explanations, access supplementary materials, and engage in meaningful discussions. Moreover, ChatGPT can facilitate the exploration of different historical perspectives, encouraging students to think critically and develop a nuanced understanding of the past. However, it is crucial to ensure that ChatGPT's responses align with the educational standards and requirements of the Vietnamese curriculum.

IV. Conclusion

ChatGPT has demonstrated an impressive ability to understand history similar to Vietnamese students. Its potential role in history teaching and learning in Vietnam lies in its ability to provide personalized

assistance, supplement traditional instructional methods, and foster critical thinking skills. While ChatGPT's performance is promising, further research is needed to refine its capabilities and align them with the Vietnamese curriculum. A balanced approach that combines the strengths of AI technology with the guidance of experienced educators is essential to create an effective and comprehensive history learning environment. By leveraging the potential of ChatGPT, Vietnam can enrich history education and empower students with a deeper understanding of the past.

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